

Patient Side Manipulator Dynamic Model Identification for the da Vinci Research Kit

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Abstract—In surgical robotics, accurate characterization of the dynamic model is crucial for developing robust control algorithms that effectively handle the interactions with the environment. This paper presents novel dynamic model for the da Vinci Research Kit (dVRK) Patient Side Manipulator (PSM) robot that employs a novel friction model definition, estimated using the superposition method. The identified model is evaluated using a model-based force estimation method.

Index Terms—Surgical robotics, robot dynamics, force sensing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Accurate dynamic modeling is crucial for creating autonomous or semi-autonomous control strategies for surgical tasks, ensuring safety. Several studies have focused on identifying the dynamic model of the da Vinci Research Kit (dVRK). For example, Fontanelli et al. used a recursive Newton-Euler approach for dynamic identification of the arms but encountered a %30 discrepancy between calculated and measured torques [1]. Others, like Sang et al., used least-square regression with screw theory and Lagrange dynamics equations for PSM dynamics [2]. Fischer et al. provided a fully open-source solution for dynamic model identification, a notable contribution [3]. Despite significant progress in developing the dynamic model for the da Vinci[®] Research Kit (dVRK), there are still inherent challenges, particularly regarding friction.

This paper presents a novel dynamic model for the PSM arm of the dVRK robot, incorporating a detailed static friction model with Coulomb and viscous friction terms, and addressing the Stribeck effect at low speeds [4]. The model's validity is confirmed through a force estimation approach, enabling computation of contact forces between the PSM and surrounding tissues. A sensorless force estimation method based on a dynamic observer validates the model [5].

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II. DYNAMIC MODEL OF THE PSM

The dynamic model of the manipulator is given by:

$$\tau = B(q)\ddot{q} + C(q, \dot{q})\dot{q} + G(q) + \tau_f + \tau_s. \quad (1)$$

The comprehensive classical friction model, which accounts for the Stribeck effect at low velocities, is utilized as follows:

$$\tau_f = \frac{2}{\pi} \arctan(c\dot{q}) \left(\left(F_c + (F_s - F_c)e^{-|\dot{q}|/\dot{q}_s} \right) + F_v\dot{q} \right), \quad (2)$$

where the terms the static friction coefficient, the Coulomb friction coefficient, and the viscous friction coefficient, respectively, and the constant c and \dot{q}_s represent linearity and Stribeck velocity parameters [4].

The dynamic model equations can be represented in linear form as: $\tau = Y_m(q, \dot{q}, \ddot{q})\beta_r$ where Y_m is the reduced regression matrix dependent on joint positions, velocities, and accelerations. β_r contains masses, centre of masses location, inertia parameters of the links, and stiffness coefficients. To excite the dynamics of the robot, finite Fourier series-based optimal excitation trajectories have been computed [6] for the identification. The following constrained optimization problem is defined based on the squared residual error to identify the dynamic parameters:

$$\operatorname{argmin}_{\beta_r} \|\tau_m - Y_m\beta_r\|^2, \text{ subject to } h(\beta_r) \leq 0, \quad (3)$$

where $h(\beta_r)$ represents the m_i inequality constraints in the search space to obtain physically consistent parameter set.

The superposition method has been applied by considering the friction model and the remaining dynamic effects separately from the dynamic model, as proposed in [7]. This can be achieved by utilizing constant velocity movements of a single joint while the remaining joints are held stationary. The consequent dynamic model when moving the robot with

Fig. 1: Measured and predicted friction torque/velocity curves.

constant velocity in positive \dot{q}_f^+ and negative \dot{q}_f^- direction becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}\tau_i(\dot{q}_f^+) &= \mathbf{G}(\dot{q}_f^+) + \tau_f(\dot{q}_f^+), \\ \tau_i(\dot{q}_f^-) &= \mathbf{G}(\dot{q}_f^-) + \tau_f(\dot{q}_f^-)\end{aligned}\quad (4)$$

where the gravitation torque $\mathbf{G}(\dot{q}_f)$ remains the same for the same joint position. Subtracting the (4), the friction torque for this velocity in a time instance can be isolated and calculated as $\tau_{fk}(\dot{q}_f) = \frac{\tau_i(\dot{q}_f^+) - \tau_i(\dot{q}_f^-)}{2}$. Moving all axes of the Patient Side Manipulator (PSM) one by one at different amplitude constant velocities, the resulting torques give a torque-velocity relationship curve, including the symmetric negative direction effect.

III. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

First, friction torque of each PSM joint is identified by moving them along constant velocity trajectories and recording average joint torque. These data points create a torque-velocity curve (marked with asterisks in Fig. 1). Using these points, a speed-torque set is generated to identify friction model parameters through fitting. Next, all PSM joints are moved simultaneously using optimal trajectories, and torque and angular motion data are recorded. Friction joint torques are subtracted from feedback torque using the superposition method. The ALPSO algorithm solves (3) to identify dynamic parameters. Evaluation is accomplished by computing relative RMSE between predicted and actual joint torques. The proposed model improves upon Wang and Fontanelli's models, achieving an average reduction of %12 and %13.2 in prediction errors, respectively.

The estimated model is validated through sensorless external force estimation using a non-linear dynamic observer, described in [5]. The residual vector denoted as \mathbf{r} is given by:

$$\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{K}_I \left(\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{q})\dot{\mathbf{q}} - \int_0^t (\boldsymbol{\tau} + \boldsymbol{\tau}_f - \mathbf{C}^T(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}})\dot{\mathbf{q}} - \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{q}) + \mathbf{r}) d\sigma \right). \quad (5)$$

If \mathbf{K}_I is sufficiently large, $\mathbf{r} \simeq \boldsymbol{\tau}_{ext}$, where $\boldsymbol{\tau}_{ext}$ denotes the external torque. Consequently, the external force can be estimated as $\hat{\mathbf{F}}_{ext} = (\mathbf{J}^T(\mathbf{q}))^\# \mathbf{r}$, where $(\mathbf{J}^T(\mathbf{q}))^\#$ represents the pseudo-inverse matrix of the transposed Jacobian matrix of the robot.

The evaluation phase consists of two sessions to validate PSM dynamic model effectiveness in force estimation. In the first session (Autonomous tests), the PSM operates autonomously along predefined trajectories to interact with

Fig. 2: (a) Autonomous tests (b) Teleoperation tests. The red lines represent the estimated residual forces, while the blue lines define the measured sensor forces.

a reference force sensor, aligning with Cartesian axes for comparison. In the second session (Teleoperation tests), a human operator controls the PSM manually, influencing real-time force estimation. Figure 2 (a) compares estimated force components (x, y, z) using the proposed method with the ATI Sensor during Autonomous tests. Fig.2 (b) shows the comparison during teleoperation. Teleoperated tests perform worse due to less smooth and inconsistent operator inputs. Success is attributed to an accurate dynamic model and parameter identification, enhancing force estimation reliability.

IV. CONCLUSION

This research presents a dynamic model for the PSM arm of the dVRK robot, focusing on parameter identification and friction modelling. Dynamic parameters are identified in two stages using the superposition method. Tests show a significant %12 reduction in RMSE relative error compared to existing models. The model is tested with an external force estimation method in autonomous and teleoperation modes.

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